

Dynamic Scheduling of Multi-DAG with Mixed-Criticality on Heterogeneous Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems

Abstract—Emerging cyber-physical systems (CPS), such as in the domains of automotive, robotics, and industrial automation, often run complex functions with different criticality levels on a heterogeneous and distributed architecture. This paper investigates dynamic scheduling of such functions, where each function is modelled by a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) with no assumption on its period or minimum inter-arrival time. Towards this, we propose two algorithms in polynomial time complexity — the second one being more aggressive in minimising the deadline miss ratio (DMR) for the highest-criticality functions. There are state-of-the-art approaches developed for dynamic scheduling of multi-DAG without properly addressing mixed-criticality, which may be applied in this context and used for comparison. Experimental results show that our algorithms outperform (in terms of DMR) these approaches in general considering all functions, with significantly better performance for the functions on the highest criticality level.

I. INTRODUCTION

Increasingly complex and diverse functions are running on distributed cyber-physical systems (CPS), with a demand of heterogeneous computing architectures. Many of the functions closely interact with the physical environment and often have different criticality levels. Taking the automotive domain as an example, there could be 100 heterogeneous Electronic Control Units (ECUs) distributed in a modern vehicle. An end-to-end automotive function runs on multiple ECUs and can be modelled as a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG). ISO26262 defines four Automotive Safety Integrity Levels (ASILs) [1], [2].

There is a trend that functions on CPS may get added or removed online depending on different scenarios, such as the use cases in automated driving, vehicle-to-everything (V2X), multimedia applications, and applications with continual “over-the-air” updating. This makes static scheduling difficult and motivates dynamic scheduling. For instance, depending on the driving context (such as highway versus urban), different sets of sensors and corresponding algorithms may be used. A recent release of AUTOSAR (AUTomotive Open System ARchitecture) [3] standard supports dynamic scheduling, where applications can be created or destroyed, with memory allocated accordingly, depending on the online needs.

Main contributions: This paper considers heterogeneous computing architectures in a distributed setup. Each function is modelled with a DAG. There is no assumption made on its release timing. We propose two dynamic scheduling algorithms for multi-DAG considering mixed-criticality, aim-

ing to minimise the deadline miss ratio (DMR)¹, both in polynomial time complexity. Algorithm 1 prioritises higher-criticality functions in scheduling while still keeping fairness to a certain extent. It also makes rescheduling decisions and adjusts the system criticality level based on the criticality levels of the incoming functions as well as the current system criticality level. Algorithm 2 is more aggressive in prioritising the functions on the highest criticality level, by introducing a shaper component in the scheduling framework. We compare these two algorithms with the state-of-the-art approaches developed for dynamic scheduling of multi-DAG, which do not properly consider mixed-criticality but can be applied in this context [4], [5]. Experimental results show that our proposed algorithms (i) perform significantly better (in terms of DMR) for the functions on the highest criticality level, which validates the effectiveness of this first work considering mixed-criticality in the dynamic scheduling of multi-DAG, and (ii) outperform the existing approaches in general considering all functions. There is also a large reduction on the execution time of the algorithms.

Organisation: This paper is organised as follows: The related work is discussed in Section II. Section III describes the models. The two proposed algorithms are presented in Section IV and V, respectively. Experimental results are reported in Section VI and Section VII concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Dynamic scheduling on mixed-criticality systems based on simple task models without considering the inter-dependencies have been studied in works like [6]–[8], which are extensions to [9] that first formalised the mixed-criticality scheduling problem. A dynamic mixed-criticality task scheduling model is proposed in [6]. Adaptive dynamic scheduling approaches are proposed in [7], [8] where the incoming workload of low-criticality tasks is regulated at runtime according to the actual demand of high-criticality tasks.

Static scheduling based on DAG models have been studied in several recent works like [10]–[16]. The federated scheduling approach for mixed-criticality systems is proposed in [10], [11], where high-utilisation tasks are assigned to dedicated processors and tasks are scheduled using a work-conserving schedule. Real-time scheduling of distributed functions in distributed embedded systems are studied in [12], [13]. Periodic multi-DAG scheduling on time-triggered sys-

¹In modern CPS, deadline misses can often be tolerated to a certain extent on the application level. There have been extensive works in this direction, such as on weakly-hard real-time systems.

Fig. 1: A CAN cluster with three busses interconnected by a central gateway.

tems is discussed in [14]. Static-cyclic scheduling for multi-criticality distributed functions with cost constraints is proposed in [15]. A meta-heuristic for scheduling multi-periodic DAGs of mixed-criticality tasks on multiprocessor systems is studied in [16].

The most relevant research to our work lies in dynamic scheduling of multi-DAG on heterogeneous distributed systems, which are studied in [4], [5], [17], [18]. A planner-directed strategy is used in [17] to schedule multiple functions dynamically. Dynamic workflow scheduling is studied in [4], [18], where a public ready list is used in [18] to keep a selected task before the selected processor is free, and the work [4] uses a wait queue for each processor and places the selected task in the wait queue if the selected processor is not idle. However, these studies in [4], [17], [18] do not consider the issue of mixed-criticality. The work [5] aims to address this issue of multiple criticality levels. However, mixed-criticality is not accounted for in the scheduling algorithm. The higher-criticality functions have no priorities over the lower-criticality ones. Only after there is a deadline miss, measures are taken to save the high-criticality functions.

III. MODELS

A. Platform Architecture

This study focuses on the platform architecture that consists of multiple heterogeneous distributed processors that are connected by networks. We take a common type of automotive CPS platform architecture that integrates multiple heterogeneous distributed ECUs with busses and a central gateway as an example to explain our models. ECUs connected to different CAN busses communicate with each other through the central CAN gateway. Fig. 1 shows such an example, where sensors receive signals from the physical components of the automobile or from the outer physical world, and under certain conditions, they may trigger the connected ECUs to release functions. We denote a set of heterogeneous distributed ECUs as $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$, whose size is $|P|$.

B. Function Model

A single function, which is to be executed by heterogeneous distributed ECUs of $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$, can be modelled as a DAG [5], [19]–[21], where the nodes stand for tasks and the edges indicate the dependencies and communication cost

between nodes. We denote the m th function in the system function set MS as $F_m = (N, W, M, C)$.

1) $N = \{F_m.n_1, \dots, F_m.n_N\}$ represents the task set containing all task nodes in F_m , and $F_m.n_i$ is the task with subscript i in F_m .

2) W is an $|N| \times |P|$ matrix, where $w_{i,k}$ is the worst-case execution time (WCET) of task $F_m.n_i$ running on p_k . Due to the heterogeneity of ECUs, the $w_{i,k}$ values of task $F_m.n_i$ on different ECUs are different. Plus, $w_{i,k}$ is replaced with an illegal value if p_k does not support task n_i . A particular task may not be allowed to run on some ECUs due to the hardware and software configuration of ECUs.

3) M is a set of communication edges, and each edge $m_{i,j} \in M$ represents the communication message from n_i to n_j . C represents the end-to-end worst-case response time (WCRT). $c_{i,j} \in C$ is the end-to-end WCRT of $m_{i,j}$, and it includes the gateway processing time of $m_{i,j}$ [5].

4) Some other attributes are defined for F_m , where $F_m.arrivalttime$ is its release time instant, $F_m.criticality$ denotes the criticality level, $F_m.lowerbound$ indicates the minimum makespan of a function when all ECUs are monopolised by the function, $F_m.deadline$ means its relative deadline and $F_m.deadline \geq F_m.lowerbound$. Periodically released functions are treated as special cases of randomly released functions in our study. Additionally, $F_m.criticality$ is related to the criticality model that is explained next.

C. Models of Criticality and Mixed-Criticality Systems

Criticality Model: The concrete specifications and identifications of criticality differ in specific industries. Industrial systems usually involve more than two criticality levels. For example, in the automotive CPS, the criticality is formalised by the ASIL concept in ISO 26262 with four levels A, B, C, and D, as discussed earlier in Section I. The criticality level of a function can be evaluated from three orthogonal dimensions, namely severity, exposure, and controllability. Severity can usually be assessed by the DMR, and if the severity of the function is different, the degree of damage caused by missing the deadline will also be different. Exposure is the relative expected probability caused only by random hardware failures in which the injury may occur and is evaluated by reliability [1]. Controllability is affected by the state of the driver at runtime.

In this study we take the identifications of criticality in ISO 26262 as an example to explain our work and focus on the severity of the problem (which can be evaluated by DMR of functions). We ignore the reliability (as the work [5], [20], [22] did) and controllability that are orthogonal problems to severity. We assume that the level of reliability for the function satisfies the need and that it is uncontrollable, ignoring the effect of human-computer interaction. Severity also involves four levels: S_0 (no injuries), S_1 (light to moderate injuries), S_2 (severe to life-threatening injuries) and S_3 (life-threatening to fatal injuries). S_0 and S_3 represent the lowest and the highest critical level among these critical levels, respectively [1]. Therefore, $S = \{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$ is used to indicate the

Fig. 2: Motivating example with four functions

severity levels set of CPS and $F_m.criticality \in S$. Plus, in this paper, we assume that all the tasks of the same function inherit the function's criticality level, i.e., $F_m.n_i.criticality = F_m.criticality$.

Mixed-Criticality System Model: In a mixed-criticality dynamic CPS, multiple distributed functions will be released concurrently and dynamically on the platform and then be executed on distributed ECUs (still using the automotive domain as an example) belonging to the set P . Specifically, one or more functions can be released at any time instant when the system is running. We denote the m th released function as F_m , and denote a set of dynamically released functions by a set $MS = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{|MS|}\}$, where $|MS|$ is the size of it. A system also has its criticality level denoted as $MS.criticality$, and it can be changed during runtime.

D. Problem Description

Given a set of dynamically released functions $MS = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{|MS|}\}$ that would be executed on a heterogeneous processor set $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$ and criticality level set $S = \{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$ in CPS, the aim is to reduce the DMRs of high-criticality functions:

$$DMR(S_x) = \frac{|MS^{\text{miss}}(S_x)|}{|MS(S_x)|}, \quad (1)$$

where $|MS^{\text{miss}}(S_x)|$ represents the number of functions with the criticality level S_x missing their absolute deadlines, and $|MS(S_x)|$ represents the number of all functions with the criticality level S_x .

E. Motivating Example

The proposed algorithms will be explained with an example with four dynamically arriving functions (with different criticality levels), as shown in Fig. 2 with some other parameters noted. The details of *lowerbound* and *deadline* of a function will be explained later. Table I shows the computation time matrices of the four functions. In accordance with the model, note that '-' is used instead of computation time if a task is not allowed to be allocated on a certain processor.

IV. ALGORITHM 1

A. Preliminaries

Lower bound. A function's lower bound refers to its minimum makespan when all processors are monopolised by

TABLE I: Computation time matrices of the motivating example in Fig. 2

(a) Computation time matrix of F_1				(b) Computation time matrix of F_2				
Tasks	$F_1.n_1$	$F_1.n_2$	$F_1.n_3$	Tasks	$F_2.n_1$	$F_2.n_2$	$F_2.n_3$	$F_2.n_4$
p_1	-	17	13	p_1	14	16	7	6
p_2	6	12	9	p_2	15	7	7	11
p_3	11	6	10	p_3	8	15	5	13
$rank_u$	47.8	28.3	10.7	$rank_u$	79.3	60	21	10

(c) Computation time matrix of F_3				(d) Computation time matrix of F_4			
Tasks	$F_3.n_1$	$F_3.n_2$	$F_3.n_3$	Tasks	$F_4.n_1$	$F_4.n_2$	$F_4.n_3$
p_1	12	13	-	p_1	8	20	20
p_2	18	10	18	p_2	13	7	15
p_3	9	-	7	p_3	18	11	8
$rank_u$	42	26	12.5	$rank_u$	44	29	14

TABLE II: Information of functions in the example				
function F_m	F_1	F_2	F_3	F_4
$F_m.abs_deadline$	34	46	56	54
$F_m.deadlineslack$	7	7	15	7

it. At the design phases in the automotive industry, algorithms that are employed to calculate functions' lower bounds must be certificated to ensure safe design required by ISO26262. The HEFT algorithm [19], is one of such certificated algorithms. It allocates the tasks in a DAG to multiple heterogeneous processors with the objective of minimising the makespan. We use it as a tool to calculate each single function's lower bound. By employing HEFT, the lower bound of a single function F_m (represented by a DAG) equals to the exit task's actual finished time calculated by HEFT. Defined by [5], each task $F_m.n_i$ has an individual lower bound $lowerbound(F_m.n_i)$ that equals to its actual finished time calculated by HEFT. The detailed calculation of HEFT can be found in [19] and will not be repeated here due to the limited space. The obtained lowerbounds of functions and tasks in the motivating example are shown in Figure 2 and Table III.

Deadline and deadline-slack. For each function, a known relative deadline is provided according to the actual physical time requirement after hazard analysis and risk assessment. It is used to limit the length of time spent between the start and end of execution of a function. In dynamic CPS, considering the time instant values on the time axis, the absolute deadline of function F_m should be calculated as follows:

$$F_m.abs_deadline = F_m.deadline + F_m.arrivalttime \quad (2)$$

The concept deadline-slack of a function is defined in [5], it represents the time slack between the relative deadline and the lower bound of the function, that is to say,

$$F_m.deadline = F_m.lowerbound + F_m.deadlineslack \quad (3)$$

Thus, according to Eq.(2) and Eq.(3) the absolute deadline of a task $F_m.n_i$ can be calculated by Eq.(4).

$$abs_deadline(F_m.n_i) = F_m.arrivalttime + lowerbound(F_m.n_i) + F_m.deadlineslack. \quad (4)$$

The obtained related values are shown in Figure 2, Table II and Table III.

TABLE III: Information of lower bounds and deadlines

Tasks	$F_{1.n_1}$	$F_{1.n_2}$	$F_{1.n_3}$	$F_{2.n_1}$	$F_{2.n_2}$	$F_{2.n_3}$	$F_{2.n_4}$	$F_{3.n_1}$	$F_{3.n_2}$	$F_{3.n_3}$	$F_{4.n_1}$	$F_{4.n_2}$	$F_{4.n_3}$
<i>lowerbound</i>	6	18	27	8	23	28	39	9	22	31	8	17	27
<i>abs_deadline</i>	13	25	34	15	30	35	46	34	43	54	35	44	54

Fig. 3: Algorithm framework

B. Scheduling Framework

The scheduling framework proposed in this paper is shown as Fig.3, which consists of several components. It is inspired by the scheduling framework in research [4], [5], the proposed component named *shaper* (the grey part in Fig.3) is the main revise in order to further reduce the deadline miss ratio of functions with highest criticality level. However, the essential contribution of our work lies in the algorithm design. Note that *shaper* is used in the next algorithm, and in this algorithm it is closed and not used.

The roles of these components are explained as follows.

- 1) The multi-functions pool holds the arrived functions.
- 2) Task priority queues. Each function F_m in multi-functions pool has a corresponding task priority queue $F_m.task_priority_queue$.
- 3) The common ready queue is denoted as $MS.common_ready_queue$. The tasks are scheduled round by round in our algorithms. In each round, the algorithm selects some tasks from several task priority queues and put them in $MS.common_ready_queue$. Therefore, this queue stores the tasks ready to be allocated in the current scheduling round.
- 4) Task allocation queues. A task allocation queue denoted as $p_k.task_allocation_queue$ is maintained for each ECU p_k . If a task in $MS.common_ready_queue$ had been selected, and the ECU for it to be allocated to was p_k , it would be inserted into $p_k.task_allocation_queue$ first. Note that $p_k.task_allocation_queue$ is not actually physically located in ECU p_k .

- 5) The cancelled tasks set. It temporarily stores tasks that have been cancelled according to some rules.

C. Trigger Events

In order to respond to changes in the system and meet the deadlines, sometimes it is necessary to cancel the previously calculated scheduling scheme of some tasks and calculate a new one. We propose the concept *trigger events* for our algorithms' design.

Definition 1: (trigger events) Trigger events refer to the events that may trigger tasks rescheduling in the process of scheduling for multi-functional mixed-criticality CPS.

We consider two types of trigger events, as defined below.

Definition 2: (new arrival trigger events) For a new arrival of one or more functions at some certain time instant during runtime, assume C_{hi} to be the highest criticality level of the new function(s), if there is at least one task among the unexecuted tasks, whose criticality level is lower than C_{hi} , this new arrival event is called a *new arrival trigger event*.

Definition 3: (deadline alert trigger events) An allocation for $F_m.n_i$ is called as a *deadline alert trigger event* if both the conditions in Eq.(5) are satisfied, where $AFT(F_m.n_i)$ is the actual finished time for $F_m.n_i$ calculated by scheduling algorithms.

$$\begin{cases} F_m.criticality > MS.criticality \\ AFT(F_m.n_i) > F_m.abs_deadline \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

A deadline alert trigger event means that it will definitely lead to the deadline missing of function F_m .

D. The Algorithm

Algorithm 1 aims at reducing the deadline miss ratio of functions and avoiding unnecessary rescheduling to improve the scheduling efficiency. It is described by the following steps.

Step (0), initialising system criticality $MS.criticality$ to be S_0 , i.e., the lowest criticality level.

Step (1), prioritising tasks for functions. For each F_m that already arrived in the multi-functions pool, put all the tasks of F_m into a queue named $F_m.task_priority_queue$ according to descending order of tasks' upward rank values (denoted as $rank_u$). The $rank_u$ values are widely used in tasks prioritising for single DAG presented function, as in [19] [5]. The $rank_u$ value of a task $F_m.n_i$ is denoted as $rank_u(F_m.n_i)$ and calculated by Eq.(6).

$$rank_u(F_m.n_i) = F_m.\bar{w}_i + \max_{F_m.n_j \in succ(F_m.n_i)} \{F_m.c_{i,j} + rank_u(F_m.n_j)\}, \quad (6)$$

where $F_m.\bar{w}_i$ is the average WCET of $F_m.n_i$ and $succ(F_m.n_i)$ is the set of $F_m.n_i$'s immediate successor tasks. See lines 14-15 in Algorithm.1. Table I shows the calculated tasks' $rank_u$ values in the motivating example.

As long as there are tasks in the task priority queues, perform step(2) to step(6).

Step (2), preparing tasks for allocation in a round. Algorithm 1 fairly treats the functions with criticality levels are not lower than $MS.criticality$. For each F_m meeting $F_m.criticality \geq MS.criticality$, only select the header task in $F_m.task_priority_queue$ and insert it in $MS.common_ready_queue$ while ensuring the tasks in $MS.common_ready_queue$ are queued in inverse order of tasks' criticality levels. Thus, the $MS.common_ready_queue$ holds the tasks ready to be allocated in current round. See lines 5-12 in Algorithm.1.

As long as there are tasks in $MS.common_ready_queue$, perform step (3) to (5).

Step (3), tasks allocating. Take out the task at the head of $MS.common_ready_queue$ (if it is not empty) and compute proper allocation decision for it. When allocating a task $F_m.n_i$, for each processor p_k in the processors set P , assuming that the selected task is allocated on p_k , calculate the earliest finish time ($EFT(F_m.n_j, p_k)$) using Eq. (7).

$$EFT(F_m.n_j, p_k) = EST(F_m.n_j, p_k) + F_m.w_{j,k}. \quad (7)$$

In Eq.(7), $EST(F_m.n_j, p_k)$ means task $F_m.n_i$'s earliest start time on p_k , and it is calculated by Eq.(8).

$$\begin{cases} EST(F_m.n_{entry}, p_k) = 0; \\ EST(F_m.n_i, p_k) = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} avail[k], \\ \max_{F_m.n_j \in pre(F_m.n_i)} \{AFT(F_m.n_j) + F_m.c_{j,i}\} \end{array} \right. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $avail[k]$ is the earliest idle time of p_k and $pre(F_m.n_i)$ means the set of immediate predecessor task of $F_m.n_i$. After that, choose the particular processor \hat{p}_k who provides the minimum earliest finish time for $F_m.n_i$ and then allocate this task on it, refer to Eq.(9). Then, mark the actual finish time of task $F_m.n_i$ as $AFT(F_m.n_i)$ as shown in Eq.(10)

$$EFT(F_m.n_j, \hat{p}_k) = \min EFT(F_m.n_j, p_k), p_k, \hat{p}_k \in P \quad (9)$$

$$AFT(F_m.n_i) = EFT(F_m.n_i, \hat{p}_k) \quad (10)$$

Then put this task $F_m.n_i$ into $\hat{p}_k.task_allocation_queue$, marking the task's actual start time (AST) and actual finish time (AFT), where $AFT(F_m.n_i) = EFT(F_m.n_i, \hat{p}_k)$ and $AST(F_m.n_i) = AFT(F_m.n_i) - F_m.w_{i,k}$. See lines 13-15 in Algorithm.1.

After that, check whether this allocation for $F_m.n_i$ is a *deadline alert trigger event* according to Definition 3. If it is, change $MS.criticality$ to be the same $F_m.criticality$ and cancel some tasks according to step(4).

Step (4), tasks cancelling. This step cancels some unexecuted tasks and is triggered by a *new arrival trigger event* or a *deadline alert trigger event* happens. Unexecuted tasks refer to the tasks that have been put into task allocation queues and have not been send to ECUs for execution. When a *deadline alert* trigger event happens, it is those unexecuted tasks who have been allocated in the current round and the previous round that are chosen to be cancelled. When a *new arrival* trigger event happens, it is those unexecuted tasks who have lower criticality levels than C_{hi} are chosen

to be cancelled. The chosen tasks will be removed to the *canceled_task_set*. Then, to prepare for the next scheduling, the remaining tasks in $MS.common_ready_queue$ will also be removed to *canceled_task_set*. Afterwards, the tasks in *canceled_task_set* will be put back to task priority queues they used to belong to. See lines 16-21 and lines 30-32 in Algorithm.1.

Step (5), resetting system criticality. Check if the function F_m that cause the *deadline alert trigger event* in step (3) is scheduled completed. If it is, reset $MS.criticality$ back to S_0 . Then clear $MS.common_ready_queue$ as in lines 22-26 in Algorithm.1.

Step (6), handling new arrived functions. If one or more new functions arrive (implemented by interrupt service routine (ISR)), check if this new arrival is a *new arrival trigger event* by using Definition 2. If it is, go to step(4) to cancel some tasks(lines 30-32 in Algorithm.1). Then, add the new arrived function or functions to the multi-function pool and preparing task priority queues for them as step (1).

Tasks executing on ECUs is relatively simple and is only driven by system time according to the scheduling results generated by the above process.

In summary, Algorithm 1 adequately considered the mixed-criticality in the whole scheduling process. Specifically,

(a) When scheduling tasks from different functions in each round, Algorithm 1 prioritises them(i.e., the tasks in $MS.common_ready_queue$) according to their criticality levels(see step (2) above and line 11 in Algorithm 1).

(b) When responding to the new arrived function(s), Algorithm 1 adaptively makes cancelling operations according to the situation of new functions and system's current criticality level and selectively cancels some unexecuted tasks(see step (6), (4) and lines 28-32 in Algorithm 1).

(c) While in the late stage of scheduling, when the *deadline miss trigger events* happen, it cancels the tasks allocated in last two scheduling rounds, adjusts the systems' criticality level and reschedules them.

The asymptotic time complexity of Algorithm 1 is $O(|MS| \cdot N_{max}^2 \cdot |P|)$, where N_{max} means the maximum number of tasks of a function in set MS .

E. The Example of Algorithm 1

This section explains Algorithm 1 algorithm with the motivating example. Fig.4-Fig.9 show the Gantt charts of scheduling process, and Table.IV shows the supporting details of the scheduling steps.

1) The system's initial criticality level is S_0 . At time instant 0, functions F_1 and F_2 arrive concurrently, as shown in Fig.2 and Fig.4), $F_1.criticality = S_3$ and $F_2.criticality = S_0$. Thus, C_{hi} is assigned to be S_3 (at this instant there are no unexecuted tasks). Tasks are prioritised in their task priority queues according to their $rank_u$ values. The related information of the example is shown in the bottom lines of Table. I and III. Algorithm 1 fairly allocated their tasks round by round, while in each single round, tasks from different functions are prioritised according to their criticality levels. As shown in line

Algorithm 1

Input: $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$, $S = \{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$, and $MS = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{|MS|}\}$

Output: Schedule results

- 1: $MS.criticality \leftarrow S_0$;
- 2: **for** ($m \leftarrow 1$; $m \leq |MS|$; $m++$) **do**
- 3: queue the tasks of F_m in descending order of $rank_u$ values into $F_m.task_priority_queue$;
- 4: **end for**
- 5: **while** (task priority queues are not all empty) **do**
- 6: **for** ($m \leftarrow 1$; $m \leq |MS|$; $m++$) **do**
- 7: **if** ($F_m.criticality < MS.criticality$) **then**
- 8: **continue**;
- 9: **end if**
- 10: $F_m.n_i \leftarrow F_m.task_priority_queue.out()$;
- 11: $MS.common_ready_queue.insert(F_m.n_i)$://insert n_i based on the descending order of criticality level
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **while** ($!MS.common_ready_queue.empty()$) **do**
- 14: $F_m.n_i \leftarrow common_ready_queue.out()$;
- 15: Assign $F_m.n_i$ to $task_allocation_queue(p_k)$ with the minimum EFT using the insertion-based scheduling strategy;
- 16: **if** ($AFT(F_m.n_i) > abs_deadline(F_m.n_i)$ && $F_m.criticality > MS.criticality$) **then**
- 17: $MS.criticality \leftarrow F_m.criticality$;
- 18: $cancelled_task_set \xleftarrow{remove} tasks$ in $MS.common_ready_queue$;
- 19: $cancelled_task_set \xleftarrow{remove} tasks$ in $task_allocation_queues$ allocated in the current and previous round
- 20: $cancelled_task_set \xrightarrow{remove\ back} task_priority_queues$
- 21: **end if**
- 22: **if** (F_m , which is the function causing the system criticality to be changed up, is scheduled completed) **then**
- 23: $cancelled_task_set \xleftarrow{remove} tasks$ in $MS.common_ready_queue$;
- 24: $cancelled_task_set \xrightarrow{remove\ back} task_priority_queues$
- 25: $MS.criticality \leftarrow S_0$;
- 26: **end if**
- 27: **end while**
- 28: **if** (new functions $MS_{new} = F_1^{new}, F_2^{new} \dots F_{|MS_{new}|}^{new}$ arrive) **then**
- 29: $C_{hi} \leftarrow$ the highest criticality of functions in MS_{new} ;
- 30: $cancelled_task_set \xleftarrow{remove} tasks$ in $task_allocation_queues$ whose criticality levels are lower than C_{hi} ;
- 31: $cancelled_task_set \xleftarrow{remove} tasks$ in $MS.common_ready_queue$;
- 32: $cancelled_task_set \xrightarrow{remove\ back} task_priority_queues$
- 33: **for** ($m \leftarrow 1$; $m \leq |MS_{new}|$; $m++$) **do**
- 34: $MS.add(F_m^{new})$;
- 35: queue the tasks of F_m^{new} in descending order of $rank_u$ values into $F_m^{new}.task_priority_queue$
- 36: **end for**
- 37: **end if**
- 38: **end while**

1 in Table.IV, $F_1.n_1$ and $F_2.n_1$ are allocated successively in the first round, $F_1.n_2$ and $F_2.n_2$ are allocated successively in the second round, where tasks scheduled in different rounds are separated by semicolon marks';'. Figure 4 shows the scheduling result where the deadlines are met.

2) When time instant turns to 10, a new function F_3 with criticality level S_1 arrives and C_{hi} is assigned to be S_1 . As shown in Figure 5, the unexecuted tasks belong to F_1 and F_2 , where $F_2.criticality < C_{hi} < F_1.criticality$. So, the unexecuted tasks of F_2 allocated in this round and previous round need to be cancelled. In Fig.5, $F_2.n_4$ and $F_2.n_3$ are marked with shadows to indicate that they have been cancelled.

3) At time instant 10, after tasks cancelling, all the tasks that have not been allocated are fairly scheduled round by round among their functions, as shown in line 3 in Table.IV and the results are shown in Fig.6. All the deadlines are met.

4) When time instant turns to 20, a new function F_4 with criticality level S_2 arrives and C_{hi} is assigned to be S_2 . The unstarted tasks belong to F_2 or F_3 , whose criticality levels are both lower than C_{hi} . Thus, tasks $F_3.n_2, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4, F_2.n_3$

Line	Fig	Current time	Trigger event	system's criticality	Operation on tasks	Operated tasks and orders
1	Fig.4	0	new arrival	S_0	Allocation	$F_1.n_1, F_2.n_1; F_1.n_2, F_2.n_2; F_1.n_3, F_2.n_3; F_2.n_4$
2	Fig.5	10	new arrival	S_0	Cancel	$F_2.n_4, F_2.n_3$
3	Fig.6	10		S_0	Allocation	$F_3.n_1, F_2.n_3; F_3.n_2, F_2.n_4; F_3.n_3$
4	Fig.7	20	new arrival	S_0	Cancel	$F_3.n_2, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4, F_2.n_3$
5	Fig.8	20		S_0	Allocation	$F_4.n_1, F_3.n_2, F_2.n_3; F_4.n_2, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4; F_4.n_3$
6	Fig.8	20	deadline alert	S_2	Cancel	$F_4.n_2, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4; F_4.n_3$
7	Fig.9	20		S_2	Allocation	$F_4.n_2, F_4.n_3$
8	Fig.9	20		S_0		$F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4$

Fig. 4: Scheduling results for F_1 and F_2 that arrive at $t=0$

Fig. 5: Tasks cancelling caused by the arrival of F_3 at $t=10$

are cancelled, as shown in line 4 in Table.IV and Fig.7.

5) At instant 20, $MS.criticality$ is still S_0 , after tasks cancelling in 4), Algorithm 1 continues to fairly schedules the functions, but when allocating $F_4.n_3$, a *deadline alert* has been found. Specifically, $F_4.n_3$ are allocated to p_3 with finish time instant 58, i.e., $AFT(F_4.n_3) = 58$. According to Eq.(4), $abs_deadline(F_4.n_3) = 54$ (as shown in Table.III). Since $AFT(F_4.n_3) > abs_deadline(F_4.n_3)$ and $F_4.criticality > MS.criticality$, this allocation is a *deadline alert trigger event* based on Definition 3. It will cause that F_4 misses its absolute deadline. See line 5 in Table IV and Figure 8.

6) At time instant 20, after the *deadline alert trigger event* has been found, $MS.criticality$ is elevated to S_2 , which equals to $F_4.criticality$. Then unexecuted tasks allocated in this round and previous need to be cancelled. In detail, the unexecuted task allocated in current round is $F_4.n_3$, the unexecuted tasks allocated in previous round are $F_4.n_2, F_3.n_3$ and $F_2.n_4$. See line 6 in Table. IV and Figure 8.

7) At time instant 20, after 6), $MS.criticality = S_2$.

Fig. 6: The scheduling results after tasks cancelling in Fig.5

Fig. 7: Tasks cancelling because of F_4 that arrives at $t=20$

Only the unexecuted tasks with higher criticality levels than $MS.criticality$ can participate in scheduling, and algorithm Algorithm 1 will fairly schedule them among the corresponding different functions. At this instant, the candidate tasks are only $F_4.n_2, F_4.n_3$. After $F_4.n_3$ has been scheduled, $MS.criticality$ is reset to S_0 , the remaining unstarted tasks $F_3.n_3$ and $F_2.n_4$ are fairly scheduled. See line 7 and line 8 in Table.IV and Fig.9. The scheduling result in Fig.9 is with no deadline missing.

V. ALGORITHM 2

In mixed-criticality systems, functions with highest-criticality levels missing their deadlines may have serious consequences. Therefore, reducing the DMR of functions with highest-criticality levels is always one goal worth working for. This section presents Algorithm 2 to further reduce the DMR of functions with highest-criticality levels.

A. Criticality-Slack

Definition 4: (criticality-slack) The criticality-slack for a single function refers to the difference between the function's criticality and the system's current criticality. For a single function F_m , given $F_m.criticality = Sx_1$ and $MS.Criticality = Sx_2$, where x_1, x_2 are integers in $[0, 3]$, the criticality-slack of F_m is denoted as $F_m.criticalityslack$ and computed as

$$F_m.criticalityslack = x_1 - x_2 \quad (11)$$

B. Scheduling Framework

This scheduling framework use a new and important component called *shaper*(the grey component in Fig.(3)).

Definition 5: (shaper) The *shaper* is a component in the scheduling framework of Algorithm 2 scheduling algorithm for multi-functional mixed-criticality CPS and is used to limit

Due to the deadline alert trigger event caused by F_4 , $MS.criticality$ is elevated from S_0 to S_2 . Tasks $F_4.n_2, F_4.n_3, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4$ have been canceled.

Fig. 8: After Fig. 7, a deadline alert is found and tasks cancelling is triggered

Fig. 9: The scheduling results after tasks cancelling caused by a deadline alert in Fig.5

the maximum tasks' amount of a given function that can join the current scheduling round. For a given function F_m , the maximum tasks' amount that can join the current scheduling round is denoted as $N_{max}(F_m)$ and computed as

$$N_{max}(F_m) = F_m.criticalityslack + 1 \quad (12)$$

In other words, for a function F_m , the *shaper* decides how many tasks in $F_m.task_priority_queue$ can be sent to $MS.common_ready_queue$ in a certain round of scheduling.

C. The Algorithm

As is known to us, traffic shapers are used in computer networks to control and regulate the speed at which data packets of different types of data traffic are injected into the network so as to achieve a certain quality of service(QoS). Inspired by this, in this work, the *shaper* is defined(see Definition 5) and used to adaptively control and regulate the speed at which the tasks of functions at different criticality levels are sent to the $MS.common_ready_queue$, in order to further reduce the deadline miss ratio of functions with high-criticality levels.

The main difference of Algorithm 2 from Algorithm 1 lies in preparing the tasks for allocation in a round. In the step (2) of Algorithm 1, the algorithm fairly pick one task in each existing

Algorithm 2

Input: $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$, $S = \{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$, and $MS = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{|MS|}\}$

Output: Schedule results

```

1: for ( $m \leftarrow 1; m \leq |MS|; m++$ ) do
2:    $F_m.task\_priority\_queue(F_m).add(F_m.n_i)$ ;
3: end for
4:  $MS.criticality \leftarrow S_0$ ;
5: while (there are tasks to be allocated) do
6:   for ( $m \leftarrow 1; m \leq |MS|; m++$ ) do
7:     if ( $F_m.criticality < MS.criticality$ ) then
8:       continue;
9:     end if
10:     $N_{max}(F_m) \leftarrow F_m.criticalityslack + 1$ , //see Eq.(11),Eq.(12)
11:     $cnt \leftarrow N_{max}(F_m)$ ;
12:    while ( $(cnt - -) \&\& (!F_m.task\_priority\_queue.empty())$ ) do
13:       $n_i \leftarrow F_m.task\_priority\_queue.out()$ ;
14:       $common\_ready\_queue.insert(n_i)$ ; //insert  $n_i$  based on the descending order of criticality level
15:    end while
16:  end for
17:  while ( $!MS.common\_ready\_queue.empty()$ ) do
18:    schedule the tasks in  $MS.common\_ready\_queue$  according to the process in lines 14-26 of Algorithm.1
19:  end while
20:  if (new functions  $MS_{new} = F_1^{new}, F_2^{new} \dots F_{|MS_{new}|}^{new}$  arrive) then
21:    handle new arrived functions as the steps in lines 29-36 in Algorithm.1
22:  end if
23: end while

```

task priority queue and put it in $MS.common_ready_queue$, thus to prepare the tasks that will be allocated in a round. While Algorithm 2, gives more opportunities to functions with higher criticality levels by employing *shaper*. The new step(2) denoted as step (2*) is described as follows, and the pseudo code of Algorithm 2 shown in Algorithm 2 presents the related new part with lines 10-15.

Step (2*), preparing tasks for allocation adaptively. By employing *shaper*, Algorithm 2 adaptively selects the tasks for allocation in a round. For a function F_m satisfying $F_m \geq MS.criticality$, keep selecting the head task in $F_m.task_priority_queue$ and put it into $MS.common_ready_queue$ till that the number of selected tasks reaches $N_{max}(F_m)$ or the $F_m.task_priority_queue$ is empty. The meaning and calculation of $N_{max}(F_m)$ is described in Definition 5.

This approach is beneficial for functions with high criticality levels, because the allocation of tasks happens round by round, and the tasks that have been selected for allocation in current round have priority over those that will be selected in the next round when choosing processors. It makes that functions with higher criticality levels are further prioritised in scheduling without always blocking the functions with lower criticality levels.

The asymptotic time complexity of Algorithm 2 is the same with Algorithm 1 is $O(|MS| \cdot N_{max}^2 \cdot |P|)$, where N_{max} means the maximum number of tasks of a function in set MS .

D. The Example of Algorithm 2

Table V shows the supporting details of the scheduling steps, Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 10-Figure 12 show the scheduling results corresponding to each steps. The scheduling results of the first two steps happened to be the same with Algorithm 1, which can be represented by Fig.4 and Fig.5 too.

TABLE V: Task allocation steps of the motivating example using Algorithm 2.

Line	Fig	Current time	Trigger event	system's criticality	Operation on tasks	Operated tasks and orders
1	Fig.4	0	new arrival	S_0	Allocation	$F_1.n_1, F_1.n_2, F_1.n_3, F_2.n_1; F_2.n_2; F_2.n_3; F_2.n_4$;
2	Fig.5	10	new arrival	S_0	Cancel	$F_2.n_4, F_2.n_3$
3	Fig.10	10		S_0	Allocation	$F_3.n_1, F_3.n_2, F_2.n_3; F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4$
4	Fig.11	20	new arrival	S_0	Cancel	$F_3.n_2, F_2.n_4, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_3$
5	Fig.12	20		S_0	Allocation	$F_4.n_1, F_4.n_2, F_4.n_3, F_3.n_2, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_3; F_2.n_4$

1) The system's initial criticality level is S_0 . When the current time of the CPS is 0, functions F_1 and F_2 arrive concurrently. Since $F_1.criticality = S_3$ and $F_2.criticality = S_0$, according to Eq.(11) and Eq.(12), $N_{max}(F_1) = 4$ and $N_{max}(F_2) = 1$. Thus, in each scheduling round, at most four tasks in F_1 are allowed to participate in scheduling, and at most one task in F_2 is allowed. Therefore, in the first scheduling round, all the three tasks of F_1 and one task of F_2 are selected into $MS.common_ready_queue$ and sorted in descending order of tasks' criticality levels. Thus, the tasks allocation order in the first round is $F_1.n_1, F_1.n_2, F_1.n_3, F_2.n_1$. Since tasks in F_1 are all allocated, in the next three rounds, one task in F_2 is selected and allocated in each round. See the line 1 in Table.V, where tasks allocated in different are separated by note ";". The scheduling results happen to be same with Fig.4.

2) When current time turns to 10, a new function F_3 with criticality S_1 arrives, so C_{hi} is assigned to be S_1 . The unexecuted tasks $F_2.n_4$ and $F_2.n_3$ belong to F_2 . The tasks are cancelled because $F_2.criticality < C_{hi}$.

3) All the unallocated tasks are scheduled as follows. Since $F_2.criticality = S_0$, $F_3.criticality = S_1$ and $MS.criticality$ is still S_0 at that time, according to Eq.(11) and Eq.(12), $N_{max}(F_2) = 1$ and $N_{max}(F_3) = 2$, with the similar process to 1), the tasks $F_3.n_1, F_3.n_2, F_2.n_3$ are allocated successively in the first round, and $F_3.n_3, F_2.n_4$ are allocated in the next round. See line 3 in Table.V. Fig.10 shows the related scheduling results, and no deadline is missed.

4) When the time instant turns to be 20, a new function F_4 with criticality S_2 arrives, so C_{hi} is assigned to be S_2 . The unstarted tasks belong to F_3 and F_2 , which both have lower criticality than C_{hi} , so they are cancelled. See line 4 in Table.V and Fig.11.

5) After 4), all the unallocated tasks are scheduled as follows. Since $F_4.criticality = S_2$, $F_2.criticality = S_0$, $F_3.criticality = S_1$ and $MS.criticality = S_0$, according to Eq. (3) and Eq.(12), $N_{max}(F_4) = 3$, $N_{max}(F_2) = 1$ and $N_{max}(F_3) = 2$, $F_4.n_1, F_4.n_2, F_4.n_3, F_3.n_2, F_3.n_3, F_2.n_3$ are allocated successively in the first round, and $F_2.n_4$ are allocated in the next round. See line 5 in Table V and Figure 12.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To evaluate the two proposed algorithms, we choose three other related algorithms for comparison, i.e., FDWS [4], FDS_MIMF [5], and ADS_MIMF [5], which solve dynamic multi-DAGs scheduling problems on heterogeneous distributed

Fig. 10: The scheduling results by Algorithm 2 after tasks cancelling in Fig.5

Fig. 11: Tasks cancelling caused by the arrival of F_4

processors. FDS_MIMF and ADS_MIMF algorithm are proposed in the state-of-the-art research. FDWS is aiming at minimizing the schedule length with high-performance concern, it does not consider the DAGs' criticality and does not cancel unexecuted tasks for the new arrivals. Its mechanism makes it a basic comparison for the above-mentioned algorithm.

A. Experimental Setting and Metrics

We mainly evaluate these works in two aspects. The first aspect concerns the scheduling results generated by these algorithms, focusing on the DMR of functions, especially the DMR of functions at the highest criticality level. The DMR of the functions in S_x criticality level is denoted as $DMR(S_x)$ (see Eq.1) and the overall DMR denoted as $DMR(overall)$ (see Eq.(13)) can reflect the overall situation. The second aspect relates to the time efficiency of the scheduling algorithms, which can be primarily reflected by the simulation time cost of the algorithms, with the average number of times the task is rescheduled as an auxiliary indicator.

$$DMR(overall) = \frac{\sum_{x=0}^3 |MS^{miss}(S_x)|}{|MS|}, \quad (13)$$

Function samples are randomly generated with the following parameter ranges. The WCET of a task and the WCRT of a message are between 100 and 400 time units, i.e., $100 \leq w_{i,k} \leq 400$, $100 \leq c_{i,j} \leq 400$. For a function, the number of tasks it contains (denoted by $|N|$) meets $8 \leq |N| \leq 23$. The deadline-slack of F_m is set as $F_m.deadlineslack = F_m.lowerbound/40$ [5]. To present the increasing complexity of CPS in both functions and platform, we consider at most 800 functions dynamically arriving and running on 100 heterogeneous ECUs distributed on automotive network. Plus, for

Fig. 12: The scheduling result by Algorithm 2 after tasks cancelling in Fig.11

each task, some ECUs ($[0,9]$) are randomly chosen to be the ones that the task cannot be allocated to.

Simulation experiments are conducted with Java and run on a PC with Intel(R) Core i7 CPU(4.00GHz) and 16GB RAM.

B. Experiments Analysis

Experiment 1. This experiment mainly evaluates the compared scheduling algorithms under different workloads. The workload, which is represented by the function set size $|MS|$, varies from 100 to 800. We limited the time range between the first and the last arrived function to be 40000 time units, and the functions arrive dynamically and randomly during the time range. The number of functions at the four critical levels are set to be equal. Based on these setting and the range of parameters described in the previous subsection, test functions are randomly generated. The obtained values of the evaluation metrics are statistical averages after a large number of repeated experiments.

Table.VI shows the deadline miss situation in Experiment 1, where the data of $DMR(overall)$ and $DMR(S_3)$ are extra graphed in Fig.14 and Fig.13 due to their importance. $DMR(overall)$ reflects the overall deadline miss situation and $DMR(S_3)$ is DMR in the highest criticality level which matters the most because missing deadlines of functions in S_3 level may cause serious life safety accidents. We have the following observations and analysis. The data of ECU utilization (calculated as Eq.14) are also shown in Tab.VI. In Eq.(14), $|P|$ is the size of ECU set $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$, $makespan(p_k)$ is the time span between 0 and the finish time instant of the last task executed on ECU p_k , $busytime(p_k)$ is the total time when there are tasks executing on p_k .

$$ECU \text{ utilization} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{|P|} busytime(p_k)}{\sum_{k=1}^{|P|} makespan(p_k)} \quad (14)$$

(a) With the increase of the workloads (reflected by $|MS|$), the $DMR(overall)$ and $DMR(S_x)$, where $x \in [0, 3]$, of all compared algorithms are increasing. It's reasonable because ECU resources are limited. Plus, because the pre-order constraint between tasks within a function, and a task has some ECUs that cannot be placed, this will cause deadline misses even when the utilization is low.

(b) As shown clearly in Table.VI and Fig.13, both Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 always have obviously lower $DMR(S_3)$

Fig. 13: $DMR(S_3)$ obtained by algorithms when the size of function set varying

Fig. 14: $DMR(overall)$ obtained by algorithms when the size of function set varying

than others, showing that the proposed algorithms exhibit obviously lower DMR of functions with the highest criticality level.

(c) In most cases when $|MS|$ varies, Algorithm 2 has 1% to 2% lower $DMR(S_3)$ than Algorithm 1 (see in Table.VI), which confirms that by further prioritizing the functions with higher criticality levels, Algorithm 2 further reduces the deadline miss ratio of functions with highest criticality levels.

(d) As shown in Table.VI, the distribution of $DMR(S_x)$ values at the four criticality levels of FDWS and FDS_MIMF is much more balanced than that of ADS_MIMF, Algorithm 1, and Algorithm 2. For the later three algorithms, the values from $DMR(S_3)$ to $DMR(S_0)$ basically show an increasing trend. This is consistent with the characteristics of the algorithms. FDWS and FDS_MIMF fairly treat all functions without considering their criticality levels, so DMR values are more even in all criticality levels. While the design in the later three algorithms consider the mixed-criticality issues where functions with higher criticality levels have lower deadline miss ratio.

(e) As shown in Fig.14 and Table.VI, Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 show lower $DMR(overall)$ than all the other compared algorithms. This indicates that the proposed algorithms does not sacrifice the DMR of lower-criticality functions too much when reducing the DMR of high-criticality functions, the overall DMRs are even lower than the existing algorithms.

Table.VII shows the simulation time cost to reflect time efficiency of the compared scheduling algorithms with ADS_MIMF as the baseline, and the average number of times a task is rescheduled is shown in Table.VI as ancillary data. ADS_MIMF is taken as a baseline, because among

$ MS $	algorithm	DMR				reschedule times per task	ECU Utilization	
		Overall	S3	S2	S1			S0
100	FDWS	0.11	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.14	0.00	0.08
	FDS_MIMF	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.07	0.12	2.03	0.08
	ADS_MIMF	0.11	0.05	0.11	0.11	0.17	2.34	0.08
	Algorithm 1	0.09	0.04	0.06	0.10	0.16	1.58	0.08
	Algorithm 2	0.09	0.02	0.06	0.10	0.18	1.63	0.08
200	FDWS	0.20	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.18	0.00	0.14
	FDS_MIMF	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.22	0.24	2.91	0.14
	ADS_MIMF	0.28	0.17	0.28	0.34	0.32	3.83	0.14
	Algorithm 1	0.18	0.05	0.14	0.26	0.26	2.42	0.14
	Algorithm 2	0.18	0.03	0.13	0.26	0.27	2.51	0.14
300	FDWS	0.29	0.28	0.26	0.30	0.30	0.00	0.20
	FDS_MIMF	0.31	0.31	0.30	0.31	0.32	3.15	0.20
	ADS_MIMF	0.38	0.23	0.34	0.42	0.52	4.21	0.20
	Algorithm 1	0.27	0.10	0.22	0.34	0.41	2.70	0.20
	Algorithm 2	0.28	0.09	0.23	0.37	0.42	2.81	0.20
400	FDWS	0.37	0.38	0.37	0.37	0.36	0.00	0.26
	FDS_MIMF	0.41	0.40	0.39	0.42	0.42	3.39	0.26
	ADS_MIMF	0.45	0.27	0.39	0.52	0.60	4.49	0.27
	Algorithm 1	0.34	0.12	0.31	0.44	0.50	2.88	0.26
	Algorithm 2	0.34	0.11	0.32	0.42	0.51	2.98	0.26
500	FDWS	0.41	0.44	0.39	0.40	0.41	0.00	0.32
	FDS_MIMF	0.47	0.47	0.48	0.47	0.46	3.41	0.31
	ADS_MIMF	0.48	0.26	0.43	0.58	0.64	4.39	0.33
	Algorithm 1	0.39	0.16	0.35	0.48	0.56	2.86	0.32
	Algorithm 2	0.39	0.15	0.39	0.47	0.55	2.94	0.32
600	FDWS	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.48	0.00	0.37
	FDS_MIMF	0.53	0.53	0.51	0.55	0.54	3.44	0.37
	ADS_MIMF	0.51	0.27	0.45	0.60	0.71	4.37	0.38
	Algorithm 1	0.44	0.17	0.38	0.55	0.64	2.89	0.37
	Algorithm 2	0.44	0.17	0.41	0.55	0.64	2.95	0.37
700	FDWS	0.54	0.54	0.52	0.55	0.54	0.00	0.42
	FDS_MIMF	0.58	0.59	0.59	0.57	0.59	3.50	0.42
	ADS_MIMF	0.53	0.28	0.48	0.63	0.75	4.36	0.44
	Algorithm 1	0.47	0.20	0.44	0.56	0.68	2.92	0.42
	Algorithm 2	0.47	0.19	0.45	0.57	0.69	2.98	0.42
800	FDWS	0.58	0.58	0.58	0.55	0.59	0.00	0.48
	FDS_MIMF	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.65	3.58	0.47
	ADS_MIMF	0.58	0.29	0.53	0.69	0.80	4.39	0.50
	Algorithm 1	0.52	0.22	0.51	0.62	0.73	2.96	0.48
	Algorithm 2	0.52	0.21	0.51	0.63	0.74	3.02	0.48

$ MS $	FDWS	FDS_MIMF	ADS_MIMF (baseline)	Algorithm 1	Algorithm 2	ADS_MIMF's time cost(s)
100	0.41	0.90	1.00	0.72	0.87	0.74
200	0.59	0.77	1.00	0.70	0.71	3.78
300	0.17	0.76	1.00	0.63	0.66	10.69
400	0.17	0.72	1.00	0.63	0.65	21.73
500	0.14	0.70	1.00	0.64	0.67	33.57
600	0.13	0.66	1.00	0.64	0.66	53.98
700	0.13	0.66	1.00	0.65	0.67	72.34
800	0.13	0.64	1.00	0.65	0.66	102.95

case	$ MS(S_3) $	$ MS(S_2) $	$ MS(S_1) $	$ MS(S_0) $
case 1	20	100	100	180
case 2	40	100	100	160
case 3	60	100	100	140
case 4	80	100	100	120

the comparison works(FDWS, FDS_MIMF, and ADS_MIMF), it considers the mixed-criticality and achieves the lowest $DMR(S_3)$. We have the following observations and analysis.

(a) Compared with ADS_MIMF, both our two algorithms have obviously improvements in time efficiency.

(b) Among the two proposed algorithms, Algorithm 2 always costs more time than Algorithm 1, that's because Algorithm 2's further strategies for reducing the deadline miss ratio of high-critical functions are more complex.

(c) FDWS always has the least time cost, which is reasonable as it calculates the allocation for a task only once and never cancels and reschedules any task. ADS_MIMF shows the most serious time consumption, mainly because that apart from the task cancellation and rescheduling due to

Fig. 15: $DMR(overall)$ obtained by algorithms when the size of function set varies in different cases

Fig. 16: $DMR(S_3)$ obtained by algorithms when the size of function set varies in different cases

deadline missing, the unconditional frequent cancellation when responding to new arrivals leads to much more rescheduling. Compared with ADS_MIMF, FDS_MIMF does not cancel and reschedule task when a deadline is missed, Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 adaptively and partially cancel and reschedule tasks, so their time consumptions lie in the middle.

Experiment 2. Missing the deadlines of functions with the highest criticality level may cause severe safety problems. In the design phase of safety-critical systems, some functions at the highest criticality level will be decomposed into multiple lower criticality level functions by SIL decomposition [1] [15]. So, take the automotive CPS as an example, the number of functions with S_3 is often less than others.

Therefore, this experiment observes the performance of algorithms when reducing the proportion of S_3 level functions in all functions. $|MS|$ is fixed to 400, the number of functions at S_2 and S_1 levels are both fixed to 100. Then reduce the number of S_3 functions from 100, and correspondingly increase the number of S_0 critical levels from 100. The configurations in four cases are shown in Table VIII. The arrival time instant of functions are in $[0, 4000]$ time units. The functions are generated in the same way as Experiment 1. The experimental results are shown in Tab.IX and Tab.X, the values are statistical averages. The data of ECU utilization(calculated as Eq.14) are also shown in Tab.IX. The $DMR(overall)$ and $DMR(S_3)$ are shown in Fig.15 and Fig.16.

As shown in Tab.IX, for $DMR(S_3)$ and $DMR(overall)$ under the configurations in all cases shown in Table.VIII, when $|MS(S_3)|$ varies between 20 and 80, the $DMR(S_3)$ and $DMR(overall)$ obtained by our algorithms are always obviously lower than existing algorithms, especially $DMR(S_3)$. Besides, although the proportion of applications in the total application changes, algorithm Algorithm 2 always has the

TABLE IX: DMR obtained by different algorithms for cases in Tab. VIII

case	algorithm	DMR					reschedule times per task	ECU Utilization
		Overall	S_3	S_2	S_1	S_0		
1	FDWS	0.36	0.37	0.34	0.36	0.37	0.00	0.26
	FDS_MIMF	0.39	0.39	0.38	0.41	0.4	3.34	0.26
	ADS_MIMF	0.44	0.18	0.27	0.43	0.56	4.30	0.26
	Algorithm 1	0.34	0.04	0.17	0.34	0.47	3.38	0.26
	Algorithm 2	0.34	0.03	0.16	0.36	0.47	3.48	0.26
2	FDWS	0.37	0.35	0.37	0.37	0.36	0.00	0.26
	FDS_MIMF	0.39	0.4	0.38	0.42	0.39	3.31	0.26
	ADS_MIMF	0.44	0.22	0.32	0.44	0.57	4.36	0.27
	Algorithm 1	0.33	0.06	0.19	0.35	0.48	3.27	0.26
	Algorithm 2	0.33	0.04	0.19	0.34	0.49	3.36	0.26
3	FDWS	0.35	0.35	0.36	0.36	0.34	0.00	0.25
	FDS_MIMF	0.4	0.41	0.4	0.41	0.4	3.31	0.25
	ADS_MIMF	0.44	0.25	0.34	0.48	0.57	4.34	0.27
	Algorithm 1	0.34	0.08	0.23	0.4	0.48	3.11	0.25
	Algorithm 2	0.33	0.07	0.23	0.4	0.47	3.22	0.25
4	FDWS	0.35	0.35	0.34	0.36	0.35	0.00	0.25
	FDS_MIMF	0.39	0.41	0.38	0.4	0.39	3.30	0.25
	ADS_MIMF	0.45	0.24	0.41	0.5	0.57	4.35	0.27
	Algorithm 1	0.33	0.09	0.28	0.42	0.46	2.96	0.25
	Algorithm 2	0.33	0.08	0.29	0.42	0.46	3.06	0.26

TABLE X: Simulation time cost comparison with ADS_MIMF as a baseline II.

case	FDWS	FDS_MIMF	ADS_MIMF (baseline)	Algorithm 1	Algorithm 2	ADS_MIMF's time cost(s)
case 1	0.16	0.73	1.00	0.76	0.79	21.02
case 2	0.16	0.71	1.00	0.72	0.75	21.84
case 3	0.19	0.73	1.00	0.69	0.72	19.55
case 4	0.16	0.72	1.00	0.66	0.69	21.57

smallest $DMR(S_3)$.

As for the time efficiency, Table.X shows the simulation time cost of the compared scheduling algorithms with ADS_MIMF as the baseline, and the average number of times a task is rescheduled is shown in Table.IX. Similar with the trends in Experiment 1, they show that Algorithm 1, Algorithm 2, and FDS_MIMF lie in the middle where ADS_MIMF is the most time consuming one and FDWS has the minimal time consumption. Compared with ADS_MIMF which has the lowest $DMR(S_3)$ among the comparison works(FDWS, FDS_MIMF, and ADS_MIMF), the proposed Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 not only have lower $DMR(S_3)$ and $DMR(overall)$ but also have advantages in time consumption. Besides, despite that Algorithm 2 is better than Algorithm 1 in $DMR(S_3)$, it always costs more time than Algorithm 1 due to the more complex strategies.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes two algorithms (i.e., Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2) addressing dynamic scheduling of multi-DAG with mixed-criticality on systems with heterogeneous distributed platform architectures. Both algorithms prioritize higher-criticality functions in scheduling, while the second one is more aggressive. As the first work considering mixed-criticality in dynamic scheduling of multi-DAG, we achieve significantly lower DMR for the functions on the highest criticality level. More generally, we perform better accounting for functions on all criticality levels. Future research could aim to further reduce the DMR. In addition, the execution time of the algorithm may have an impact on the scheduling and should be minimised. More work can be done in this direction from both the software and hardware perspectives.

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